

Performance Comparisons of YOLOv8 and YOLOv5 for Drone Detection

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Abstract: YOLO is a neural network algorithm for deep learning that is extensively used in computer vision applications due to its superior performance. The most recent version is YOLOv8, which improves in terms of both speed and accuracy. It is fascinating to consider, when compared to YOLOv5, which was the previous successful version. This study evaluates the performance of YOLOv5 and YOLOv8 for object detection to detect flying objects, including drones as a major class and airplanes, birds, and helicopters as three minor classes. More than 6,000 images were gathered and trained as a custom dataset on a local workstation. The comparison was done using model sizes s, m, and l. YOLOv8l demonstrated superior mean average precision (mAP) from all six architecture models with a mAP50 of 0.9940 and also holds the best mAP50-95 of 0.8480.

Keywords: *Computer vision, Deep learning, YOLO, Drone detection, Object detection*

1. Introduction

Currently, the performance of computers used to develop artificial intelligence models is increasing, thus decreasing the duration of time required to calculate equations in artificial intelligence algorithms. For that reason, the application of integrated artificial intelligence models in various situations is increasing. Object detection has been a very popular and interesting algorithm in recent years due to its ability to identify and locate various objects as desired. This algorithm has found applications in various areas such as human fall detection, product inspection in industrial settings, autonomous driving, danger surveillance, robotic vision, and more. Currently, there are many object detection algorithms, such as R-CNN [1], Fast R-CNN [2], Faster R-CNN [3], SSD [4], and YOLO, which have obtained significant interest in the present.

YOLO is one of the most effective algorithms for object detection, with great speed and accuracy. YOLO [5] stands for “You Only Look Once”, which is a popular open-source algorithm framework for computer vision developments [6]. The most recent version is YOLOv8 [7, 8], which Ultralytic made available in January 2023. In addition to object detection, object

tracking, instance segmentation, image classification, and pose estimation are also supported. YOLOv5 is another previous version with excellent performance, so it is fascinating to compare the object detection performance of YOLOv8 with YOLOv5 because their performance is so close.

In this study, the model was trained with a custom dataset that included drones, airplanes, helicopters, and birds by using different structure networks from YOLOv5 and YOLOv8 with model sizes of s, m, and l, comparing the capabilities of the model that were archived from the training process to find the best performing model for drone detection. To avoid false detection, the three classes of birds, airplanes, and helicopters were added to the minor class as well.

2. Methodology

2.1 YOLOv5

YOLOv5 [9, 10] used the CSPDarknet53 backbone that had been modified with Stem. A stem is a series of convolutional layers that have a large window size to reduce memory use and computation costs that are used to extract features from input images. The neck of YOLOv5 utilizes SPPF and a modified CSP-PAN to mixed and combine input image features before providing these to the prediction process. The head of YOLOv5 is similar to that of YOLOv3 [11], which predicted objects by using features from the neck layer and determining out the probability of each object. Based on the structural complexity of YOLOv5, 10 architectures are currently available. YOLOv5n, YOLOv5s, YOLOv5m, YOLOv5l, YOLOv5x, YOLOv5n6, YOLOv5s6, YOLOv5m6, YOLOv5l6, and YOLOv5x6 + TTA.

2.2 YOLOv8

The latest version of the YOLO algorithms, released in January 2023, is known as YOLOv8. This version was developed by Ultralytics, the same company that developed YOLOv5 [12]. YOLOv8 is capable of performing a variety of tasks, such as object detection, segmentation, pose estimation, tracking, and classification. The backbone of YOLOv8 [13] uses a modified CSPLayer called the C2f module (cross-stage partial bottleneck with two convolutions) to improve

detection accuracy [14]. The neck layer of YOLOv8 uses a combination of Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) and Path Aggregation Network (PAN), known as FPN-PAN, to combine features of input images provided by different layers in the network. The output layer of YOLOv8 uses the activation function of the sigmoid function for the objectness score, which represents the probability that a bounding box is an object, followed by calculating the probability of each possible class with the Softmax function [15]. YOLOv8 supports multiple integrations for annotation, training, and deployment across a wide range of tasks. The YOLOv8 packages can be installed and used through the Command Line Interface (CLI) by installing the YOLOv8 packages from Python Package Index (PyPI). Based on the structural complexity of YOLOv8, five architectures are currently available. They are YOLOv8n, YOLOv8s, YOLOv8m, YOLOv8l, and YOLOv8x.

3. Experiment

3.1 Experiment dataset

Images of drones, birds, airplanes, and helicopters from public resources were collected. In addition, Python scripts gathered images from some videos. The images that are collected have different attitudes, angles, and backgrounds, ensuring variability in the dataset. The dataset consisted of 6,844 images then, split to 80:10:10 for a train, test and validation dataset and use to train the model on both YOLOv5 and YOLOv8. The quantity per training set, test set, and validation set were 5,361, 717, and 766, respectively.

Collected images were labeled by labeling on Roboflow and divided into 4 classes, consisting of “drone”, “airplane”, “helicopter”, and “bird”. Fig. 1. Is an example of a dataset.

Fig. 1. Example image dataset

3.2 Experiment environment

In this study, the model was trained on a PC with Windows 11 Professional. The CPU is an Intel Core I9-11900 with 128 GB of memory, and the GPU is an RTX 3080 with CUDA 11.7. A virtual environment in Anaconda 3 was set up using PyTorch 2.0.0 for the training process between YOLOv5 and YOLOv8.

3.3 Model training

YOLOv5s, YOLOv5m, YOLOv5l, YOLO8s, YOLO8m, and YOLOv8l were used for this study to compare the performance of YOLOv5 and YOLOv8 for drone detection. The duration of training for each model is shown in Fig. 2. Each model was trained with 200 epochs with images size of 640x640 pixels, batch size of 8, workers of 8, and other hyperparameter were left at their default value.

Fig. 2. Duration of model training

4. Result

The trained model was evaluated with mAP50, mAP50–95, precision, and recall. The results of all models are shown in Fig. 3, consisting of mAP50, mAP50–95, precision, and recall. According to the experimental findings, the average mAP50 for all models is over 0.9, and the average mAP50–95 is over 0.7. In addition, precision and recall of archived scores are over 0.95. The performance of all models in the training terms of mAP50 and mAP50–95 is shown in Fig. 4 and 5, respectively. The YOLOv8l architecture outperformed other models during this experimental training in terms of mAP50 and mAP50–95.

Fig. 3. YOLOv5 (s, m, l) and YOLOv8 (s, m, l) model’s performance

Fig. 4. YOLOv8’s mAP@0.5

Fig. 5. YOLOv8's mAP@0.5-0.95

The confusion matrix heat map [16] is an additional performance assessment tools. The YOLOv8l model was evaluated using 717 photos from the test set, as shown in Fig. 6. The results indicate that the drone, a major class, obtains 99% TP (true positive), the airplane, which achieves 100% TP, is the best, and the bird, which reaches 84% TP, is the worst. An example of YOLOv8l output when testing detection images is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6. Confusion matrix of testing using YOLOv8l

Fig. 7. Example of drone detection as output from YOLOv8l

5. Conclusions

In this research, the objective detection performance of YOLOv5 and YOLOv8 was evaluated. For a fair comparison, this study used the same dataset and configuration. More than 6,000 images have been annotated by Roboflow into four categories: "drone", "airplane", "helicopter", and "bird". YOLOv8l demonstrated superior mAP50 and mAP50–95 more than other model architectures that were selected; this model's archives reach mAP50 at 0.9940 and mAP50–95 at 0.8480. In terms of precision score, YOLOv5s achieve a best precision score of 0.9887. For the recall score, YOLOv5l got the highest score of 0.9916. For the conclusion, YOLOv8 performs better performance compared to YOLOv5 in terms of mAP but might take longer training time and lag for precision and recall.

YOLOv8 is the most recent and impressive version in terms of speed and accuracy, and it also supports a variety of computer vision tasks. However, this version has just been released and will be further developed in the future. Each version of the YOLO algorithm has distinct benefits, allowing users to select the version that best meets their requirements.

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